

Acknowledgement

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Studies on some Oxozirconium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Schiff Base Complexes

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MANY Schiff base complexes of transition metals using aldehydes and ketones have been reported from this laboratory¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of some Schiff base complexes of oxozirconium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) using analytical, conductance, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared using the following two steps. (a) A mixture of furan-2-aldehyde (0.01

mol, 1.66 ml) in methanol (25 ml), glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) and aniline (0.01 mol, 1.82 ml) or ethylene diamine (0.005 mol, 1.32 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. When the colour of solution changed from red to brown, the solvent was distilled off and the ligands were crystallised out from the light brown fraction after running the solution over tlc plates and analysed. (b) A mixture of appropriate oxometal chloride or acetate (0.01 mol) and ligand L₁ (0.02 mol, 3.42 g) or L₂ (0.01 mol, 2.16 g) was refluxed for 5 h. The solid complexes were crystallised using petroleum ether, purified by running over tlc plates, dried and analysed (Table 1).

The thiocyanate and perchlorate complexes were prepared by adding ammonium thiocyanate/potassium perchlorate to the solution of oxometal chlorides and ligand L₁ or L₂ in dry methanol (50 ml) and refluxing the mixture for 5 h. After filtering ammonium/potassium chloride, the complexes were crystallised out as in the previous case (Table 1).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies. The molar conductances were measured in MeOH and DMSO on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz).

Results and Discussion

The theoretical condensation reactions show that ligand L₁ is bi- and L₂ is tetradentate in nature and hence their complexes should possess 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 stoichiometry respectively, which are confirmed by analytical data. The conductance of all complexes are in the usual range of 1 : 2 electrolytes (40–60 in DMSO, 160–220 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in MeOH) and hence these are formulated as [ZrO(L₁)₂ or (L₂)]X₂ and [UO₂(L₁)₂ or (L₂)]X₂, where X = Cl⁻, ClO₄⁻, SCN⁻ and CH₃COO⁻.

The ir spectra of free ligands reveal bands at 1 600, 1 540, 1 500 and 1 450 cm⁻¹ due to aromatic and heterocyclic ring vibrations and these show a positive shift in case of the complexes². A sharp band at 1 610 cm⁻¹ (azomethine stretch) of the free ligand shifts to 1 590 cm⁻¹ in case of the complexes indicating the coordination through its nitrogen atom³.

The ν_{O-U=O} and ν_{Zr=O} bands are observed at 910 ± 5 and 970 ± 5 cm⁻¹ respectively⁴. Other bands were observed at 511 (ionic chloride)⁵, 2 050, 750, 485 (uncoordinated thiocyanate)⁶, 1 085, 620 (uncoordinated perchlorate)⁷ and 2 936, 1 414, 930, 675 cm⁻¹ (uncoordinated acetate ion)⁸. These spectra are in accordance with the conductance data of the complexes.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of ligand L₁, the CH protons appear as singlet at δ 2.05 (2H) whereas the heterocyclic and the phenyl ring protons merge

NOTES

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conduct.* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		M	C	H	N	
$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{NO}(\text{L}_1)$	Brownish red	—	76.85 (77.19)	5.70 (5.26)	8.52 (8.18)	—
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2(\text{L}_2)$	Brown	—	66.10 (66.66)	5.90 (5.55)	13.20 (12.98)	—
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Brown	15.70 (15.37)	46.60 (46.15)	4.50 (4.14)	4.90 (4.85)	162.30 ^a
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_1)_2](\text{SCN})_2$	Brown	15.58 (16.10)	50.25 (50.97)	2.85 (3.10)	9.55 (9.90)	54.70 ^b
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_1)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Dark brown	13.56 (14.04)	40.20 (40.74)	2.50 (2.77)	4.96 (4.32)	58.25 ^b
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_1)_2](\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Reddish brown	32.20 (32.60)	42.18 (42.73)	3.52 (3.28)	3.68 (3.24)	47.10 ^b
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Blackish red	33.78 (34.25)	38.05 (38.64)	2.18 (2.63)	2.70 (2.04)	59.18 ^b
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_1)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Brown	28.77 (29.35)	32.10 (32.54)	2.50 (2.22)	3.10 (3.45)	47.10 ^b
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$	Black	22.34 (22.09)	36.05 (36.50)	3.52 (3.04)	7.50 (7.10)	190.22 ^a
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_2)](\text{SCN})_2$	Brown	19.98 (20.70)	35.90 (35.50)	2.25 (2.73)	9.92 (9.56)	189.86 ^a
$[\text{ZrO}(\text{L}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Brown	20.88 (21.53)	27.10 (27.58)	2.60 (2.29)	5.58 (5.36)	185.15 ^a
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_2)](\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Reddish brown	38.99 (39.41)	31.25 (31.78)	2.90 (2.64)	4.95 (4.63)	189.74 ^a
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$	Brown	42.13 (42.73)	25.20 (25.84)	2.60 (2.15)	5.40 (5.02)	193.29 ^a
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_2)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Brown	34.27 (34.75)	21.42 (21.01)	2.05 (1.75)	4.52 (4.08)	191.68 ^a

*Solvent : ^aMeOH, ^bDMSO.

together and appear as a broad multiplet in the region δ 6.10–7.10 (8H). Shiftings of both these signals shifted and are observed in the complexes at δ 2.20 and 7.90. Similarly, in the nmr spectra of the ligand L_2 the CH_2 and CH protons appear as singlets at δ 3.85 (4H) and 2.10 (2H) and the heterocyclic protons appear at δ 6.10–7.10 (6H) as a multiplet. In its complexes the former two protons shift to δ 4.20 and 2.60 but appear as singlets, while the heterocyclic ring protons appear at δ 8.05. The shifts in the position of these signals may be attributed to the coordination of the ligand to oxo-metal cations.

On the basis of the above discussion it may be suggested that both the ligands coordinate to oxo-metal ions in a planar fashion through their azomethine nitrogen atoms while the single oxygen atom of ZrO^{2+} and both the oxygen atoms of UO_2^{2+} ions are placed at the axial positions of a square-pyramid and octahedron respectively, thus projecting outside the plane of the coordinated ligands.

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